

22NRM06 ADMIT

Deliverable D6:

Validation report on the traceability of current reference measuring systems, up to 2 kA for AC or DC, with superimposed frequency components up to 150 kHz including the description of the reference measuring systems, their traceability and a statement of measurement uncertainties

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Glossary

AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
MV	Medium Voltage
EPM	European Partnership on Metrology
NMIs	National Metrology Institutes
VT	Voltage Transformer
DUT	Device Under Test
AWG	Arbitrary Waveform Generator
DAQ	Data Acquisition System / Module
UD	Universal Divider
HF	High Frequency
HV	High Voltage
RMS	Root Mean Square
RC	Resistor-Capacitor (circuit or divider)
FFII	Fundación para la Investigación y el Desarrollo de la Industria (Spain)
INRIM	Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (Italy)
METAS	Federal Institute of Metrology (Switzerland)
VSL	VSL Dutch Metrology Institute (Netherlands)
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre, Centre for Metrology MIKES (Finland)
MSO	Mixed Signal Oscilloscope
PFG	Power Frequency Generator
RCVD	Resistive-Capacitive Voltage Divider
SF	Scale Factor
SFS	Sinusoidal Frequency Sweep
PXI	PCI eXtensions for Instrumentation
PLL	Phase Locked Loop
LFRD	Low Frequency Reference Device
HFRD	High Frequency Reference Device
LVD	Low Voltage Divider
LFA	Low Frequency Amplifier
HFA	High Frequency Amplifier
HFVT	High-Frequency Voltage Transformer

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1 Summary

This deliverable describes the reference current measurement systems developed within Task 3.2 of the ADMIT project for the traceable characterisation of current transformers up to 2 kA and frequencies up to 150 kHz. The report provides an overview of the measurement concepts, the implemented reference sensors and comparators, and the associated traceability chains to the SI.

Particular attention is given to the extension of current measurement capabilities into the supraharmmonic frequency range, including the treatment of frequency-dependent effects in sensors, instrumentation, and measurement setups. The report further presents typical uncertainty levels achievable with the developed systems and provides representative uncertainty budgets for selected configurations.

The described reference measurement systems form a metrological basis for future calibration and testing activities and support ongoing developments in standardisation for wideband instrument transformers.

2 Introduction

Instrument transformers (ITs) play a central role in monitoring, protection, and power quality assessment in modern medium-voltage (MV) electrical networks. Due to the increasing penetration of power-electronic devices and renewable energy sources, these networks are now subject to significant harmonic and supraharmmonic disturbances extending well beyond the traditional power-frequency range. Accurate and traceable measurement of such phenomena therefore requires ITs whose performance is well characterised not only at 50 Hz or 60 Hz, but also over an extended frequency range reaching at least 150 kHz [1].

The ADMIT project addresses this need by developing and validating reference measurement systems and methodologies for the characterisation of both current transformers (CTs) and voltage transformers (VTs) under realistic operating conditions, including superimposed higher-frequency components. Within this framework, Work Package 3 focuses on the development of reference setups, traceability chains, and uncertainty evaluation methods to support wideband CT characterisation. The results support emerging standardisation efforts and underpin the development of a sound metrological infrastructure for future calibration and testing activities.

This deliverable, D6, describes the reference current measurement systems developed within Task 3.2 of the project. It provides detailed information on the measurement concepts, the implemented reference sensors and comparators, and the associated traceability chains to the SI. In addition, the report presents uncertainty evaluations and typical performance levels across the frequency range from DC and power frequency up to 150 kHz.

In parallel, Deliverable D5 addresses the corresponding developments for voltage transformers. Together, these deliverables describe the metrological infrastructure developed within ADMIT for the traceable characterisation of instrument transformers over an extended frequency range.

3 Scope within the ADMIT project

Deliverable D6 fulfils the objectives of Activity A3.2.8 and represents the outcome of Task 3.2, “Current reference measurement systems”, within Work Package 3. The work reported in this deliverable focuses on:

- the selection and characterisation of suitable reference current sensors,
- the development and upgrade of comparator systems for wideband measurements,
- the establishment of traceable measurement chains linking these systems to the SI, and
- the evaluation of measurement uncertainties across the extended frequency and current range.

The results presented in this report complement the Good Practice Guide for current generation (Deliverable D4) and provide the metrological validation necessary to support future calibration and testing services, as well as contributions to standardisation activities within IEC TC 38.

The primary objective of Task 3.2 is to establish reference current measurement systems suitable for the traceable characterisation of CTs at current levels up to 2 kA and for frequencies from DC and power frequency

up to 150 kHz. The target performance is defined in relation to the accuracy requirements of CTs used for power quality and disturbance measurements in medium-voltage grids, as determined in WP1.

In particular, the reference systems must support:

- accurate determination of ratio error and phase displacement,
- operation under steady-state and, where applicable, transient regimes,
- uncertainty levels significantly lower than the CT accuracy limits over the full frequency range.

Activities A3.2.1 to A3.2.5 addressed the selection, development, characterisation, and traceability of current reference measurement systems at several partner institutes. Different technical approaches were used, reflecting the different existing infrastructures and expertise among the partners.

The resulting systems include combinations of reference current transformers, broadband current shunts, high-accuracy sampling comparators, and calibrated power analysers. Together, these systems form the basis for the traceability chains validated in this deliverable.

4 Description of Reference Current Transducer Measurement Systems

4.1 VSL, the Netherlands

4.1.1 Measurement concept

The VSL reference current measurement system is designed for the traceable characterisation of window-type current transformers (CTs) in the frequency range from 50 Hz up to 150 kHz, covering both steady-state single-frequency excitation and power-frequency currents with superimposed higher-frequency components. The system supports CT characterisation over a wide current range, with primary currents up to 2 kA at power frequency and reduced-amplitude current components of up to 20 A at the highest frequencies, consistent with the objectives of Task 3.2 of the ADMIT project.

The measurement principle is a ratio-based comparison method, in which the CT under test (DUT) is measured against a reference CT sensing the same primary current [2]. From the complex ratio of the simultaneously measured secondary currents, the magnitude ratio error and phase displacement of the DUT are obtained. This approach avoids the need for direct measurement of wideband high-current primary current and is well suited for the extended frequency range up to 150 kHz, as discussed in detail in [3][3].

For applications where reduced complexity is preferred and higher uncertainties are acceptable, a direct primary–secondary measurement method is also employed, in which both primary and secondary currents are measured simultaneously using a calibrated sampling power analyser. This second approach serves mainly routine measurements.

4.1.2 Current Generation

The current generation itself is not part of the reference measurement chain but provides the controlled excitation required for CT characterisation. At VSL, power-frequency currents up to 2 kA and high-frequency currents up to 150 kHz are generated using dedicated current sources and broadband amplifiers, as described in detail in Deliverable D4.

From the perspective of the measurement system, the current-generation part is characterised by two separate primary conductors fed through both the DUT and the reference CT: one for the power-frequency fundamental component and the other for the superimposed distortion components. The primary loops are designed to have low inductance to support high-frequency currents. During operation, controlled current ramp-up and stabilisation are applied before the data acquisition to ensure reproducible measurement conditions. Proper grounding is implemented at the low terminals of the CT secondary outputs to minimise common-mode effects and unwanted coupling.

4.1.3 Measurement System

The measurement system is entirely located on the secondary side of the CTs and is independent of the current generation hardware (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the measurement setup where a high-current source feeds both the DUT CT and the reference CT [3]. The secondary outputs are recorded using a power analyser for ratio comparison.

For ratio-based CT characterisation, the secondary currents of the DUT and the reference CT are measured simultaneously using a wideband sampling power analyser operated as a precision sampling ammeter. A Yokogawa WT5000 power analyser is used, equipped with interchangeable current input modules with selectable current ranges for secondary currents typically in the 0.2 A to 5 A range. The analyser measures the voltage drop across its internal shunts with synchronous sampling, allowing determination of both magnitude ratio and phase displacement of the secondary currents over the full frequency range up to 150 kHz. Since the ratio of two currents is measured, the gain error of the modules is cancelled by interchanging the two modules and repeating the measurement.

The reference CT in this system was an NRC electronically compensated CT with an accuracy of about 1 ppm at 50 Hz and a nominal turns ratio of 100:1. The CTs use internal compensation electronics to ensure low errors (less than 20 ppm and 20 μ rad) up to 5 kHz [4][4]. However, the internal feedback amplifier bandwidth restricts the effectiveness of compensation beyond a few kilohertz, which has an impact on high-frequency performance. This impact results in differences measured when two similar reference CTs with minor differences in feedback electronics are compared using this method, at which one of the two CTs is considered the reference and the other the DUT (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Magnitude ratio error and phase difference between secondary currents of CT A and CT B, measured using the ratio method with CT A as a reference. Up to 10 kHz, the magnitude ratio and phase displacement differences between the CTs is less than 10 ppm and 10 μ rad, respectively. Increasing deviations are observed at higher frequencies.

For the simplified primary–secondary measurement method, the same sampling power analyser is used to directly measure both the CT primary and secondary currents. Although this method results in higher uncertainties and is limited to primary currents of 30 A only, it provides a practical measurement chain for routine use for lower-current applications.

Figure 3. Primary-to-secondary current magnitude ratios and phase displacements of two similar reference CTs, A and B, measured using the direct measurement method at 10 A primary current. Differences become more pronounced above 10 kHz.

4.1.4 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

Traceability of the VSL CT measurement setup is established through two complementary routes that share common calibrated references. Across both routes, frequency-dependent effects such as bandwidth limitations, phase shifts, and sampling-related errors are addressed through calibration data and correction models.

At high primary current levels, traceability is realised by direct comparison of the 100:1 reference CT against calibrated current shunts. The primary conductor is looped 20 times through the CT core to effectively increase the primary-to-secondary ratio, enabling operation at favourable secondary current and voltage levels. The secondary output of the reference CT is connected in series with a broadband calibrated 1 A shunt (1 Ω nominal), while a broadband calibrated 5 A shunt (0.2 Ω nominal) provides the reference voltage in parallel. With 20 primary turns, a primary current of 5 A per turn produces 1 A at the CT secondary; the voltages across the 1 A and 5 A shunts are then nominally equal, providing ratio and phase comparison with low uncertainty. These voltages are measured with the synchronised voltage inputs of a broadband power analyser, and frequency-dependent amplitude and phase corrections of the shunts are shown to be negligible based on traceable calibration against resistance and AC current standards. Typical relative uncertainties achieved at 150 kHz with this route are of the order of parts in 10^4 and few tenths of mrad [3][3].

For applications where reduced complexity is preferred, traceability is achieved by measuring both primary and secondary current directly using the sampling ammeters of the power analyser, and obtaining the CT complex ratio error from the measured current ratio. In this route, calibration of the power analyser current channels is performed using the same 1 A and 5 A calibrated shunts, together with a calibrated AC voltage reference standard, to establish amplitude and phase accuracy of the sampling system across the relevant frequency range. The relative uncertainties at 150 kHz are typically the order of parts in 10^3 and few mrad, reflecting the simpler measurement chain and the additional dependence on analyser channel calibration and combined system effects.

4.2 METAS, Switzerland

4.2.1 Measurement concept

The METAS reference current measurement system is designed for the metrological characterization of window-type current transformers (CTs), with a particular focus on wideband performance up to 150 kHz.

The measurement principle is based on a comparative approach between the primary current injected into the CT, measured using a high-precision shunt (reference), and the secondary current output by the CT, measured indirectly as a voltage signal.

The magnitude ratio error of the CT is determined by comparing the measured transformation ratio with the nominal ratio. The phase displacement is obtained from the phase difference between the primary and secondary signals.

To enable testing at high equivalent currents while maintaining wideband performance, the system uses multi-turn configurations on the primary side of the CT. This allows an increase of the effective primary current (typically, up to 2 kA) without requiring the current generation chain to deliver the full current directly.

4.2.2 Current Generation

The current generation chain consists of a function generator, defining the test signal waveform and frequency, and a transconductance amplifier, converting voltage into current.

The amplifier is capable of delivering: up to 100 A with frequencies up to 100 kHz on high current ranges and up to 150 kHz on low current ranges.

At higher frequencies, bandwidth limitations require a reduction of the output current magnitude. This limitation is mitigated by using multiple turns on the primary side of the CT. In this way, the system is capable of generating a primary current of 20 A at a frequency of 150 kHz using a 2 A input with 10 turns.

The amplifier output is equipped with connectors suitable for different current levels (125 A and 32 A), providing flexibility depending on the test configuration.

4.2.3 Measurement System

The measurement system is based on the simultaneous acquisition of primary and secondary signals using a high-precision power analyser such as the Yokogawa WT5000.

Figure 4. Schematic representation of the METAS measurement setup.

The primary current is measured using high-precision shunts, which convert current into a proportional voltage.

Special care is taken regarding Kelvin connections, minimization of parasitic inductance and thermal stability.

The CT secondary current is measured via a shunt providing a voltage proportional to the secondary current. Proper grounding is provided at the lower terminals of the CT's secondary outputs to minimize common-

mode effects and unwanted coupling.

Both primary and secondary voltages are acquired on the voltage inputs of the analyzer. The system enables amplitude measurement and phase difference determination.

The different component of the measurement systems are calibrated at each combination of current magnitude and frequency of interest. Magnitude and phase corrections are applied to each measurement channel to compensate for systematic errors.

Figure 5. Magnitude ratio error and phase difference between secondary currents of CT and shunt. Increasing deviations are observed at higher frequencies.

4.2.4 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

The metrological traceability of the system is ensured through the following element:

- The voltage inputs of the power analyzer are calibrated using a reference calibrator. Corrections are applied to account for gain errors and inter-channel phase deviations.
- The current shunts are calibrated by a specialized laboratory of METAS, ensuring traceability to the International System of Units (SI). Although the calibration is performed in DC, the shunts exhibit low frequency dependence, allowing their use in AC conditions with controlled uncertainty over the frequency range of interest.
- Additional uncertainty contributions arise from cable inductance and capacitance, electromagnetic coupling, multi-turn configurations (increased inductance and possible resonances).

The overall measurement system exhibits a typical relative uncertainty in amplitude on the order of a few hundreds ppm. This uncertainty is mainly dominated by the accuracy of the Yokogawa WT5000, with minor contributions from the calibrated shunts.

The typical phase uncertainty is on the order of a few tenths of milliradians, primarily limited by the inter-channel phase accuracy of the measurement instrument. Additional contributions from cabling and parasitic effects may become significant at higher frequencies.

4.3 FFII, Spain

4.3.1 Measurement concept

The FFII reference current measurement setup targets traceable characterization of current transformers over an extended bandwidth, from 50 Hz up to 150 kHz. The setup is intended to cover both single-frequency steady-state excitation and power frequency operation with superimposed higher-frequency components. The applicable current range spans up to 2 kA at power frequency, while the injected high-frequency components are generated at reduced amplitude, up to 50 A from 9 kHz to 150 kHz.

The primary CT characterization at FFII is based on a ratio comparison: the DUT and the reference CT are subjected to the same primary current, and their secondary currents are acquired synchronously. The DUT ratio error and phase displacement are then obtained from the complex ratio between the two measured secondary currents. The reference CT used at FFII are a Tettex model 4764CL for 50 Hz and a Fluke i800s for 9 kHz to 150 kHz, and the acquisition, ratio evaluation and phase displacement measurements are performed with a Yokogawa WT 5000.

4.3.2 Current Generation

In the FFII setup, there are two primary conductors passing through both the DUT and the reference CT. One of the conductors is included in a loop that carries the power frequency current, while the second conductor is included in a second loop that carries the superimposed component.

A dedicated high current source composed of XXX feeds the 50 Hz loop. The harmonic components are generated by a calibrator fluke 5500, which feeds a power amplifier Ae Techron 9110, which feeds the high frequency current loop. Figure 6 shows a drawing and a picture of the calibration test setup.

Figure 6. Drawing of the calibration test setup.

4.3.3 Measurement System

The fluke i800s is a ferrite core current clamp connected to a calibrated resistance with a nominal output ratio of 10 mV/A. It was selected as the main reference equipment for the reference measuring system due to its linear and stable behavior throughout the frequency wide-band up to 150 kHz.

Figure 7 and Figure 8 show the scale factor and phase error of the probe throughout the frequency.

Figure 7. Reference measuring system magnitude ratio error.

Figure 8. Reference measuring system phase error.

Data acquisition is performed with the Yokogawa WT5000’s Data Streaming feature to save waveform in an external computer. The waveform is then analyzed using a sinusoidal wave fitting algorithm to isolate the high-frequency component and enhance waveform resolution. Ratio magnitude and phase displacement are calculated using a signal correlation method.

Figure 9 shows a comparison of the sinusoidal fitting with a wideband pass filter, suppressing the fundamental 50 Hz component. It is observed that the fitted signal maintains the waveform parameters while eliminating background noise.

Figure 9. Comparison of wave analysing methods

4.3.4 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

The metrological traceability of the system is ensured through the calibration of the current clamp against a coaxial shunt TRANSMILLE AC/DC 100A. This shunt is calibrated from 50 Hz to 100 kHz and its AC/DC ratio is characterized to be in the ppm range through all frequencies.

The combined uncertainty for the current transformation ratio is $\pm 0.39\%$ at 9 kHz and $\pm 2.7\%$ at 150 kHz. The combined uncertainty for the overall phase displacement of the calibration set up is 0.9 crad in all frequencies.

4.4 RISE, Sweden

4.4.1 Measurement concept

At RISE an AC current generation system has been developed using two current sources suitable for calibration of window type measurement systems. One source generates 50 to 1 kHz up to 2 kA and the other source generates supraharmonics from 2 to 20 kHz up to 100 A and 20 A for frequencies up to 150 kHz. The device under test (DUT) is then connected to both sources.

4.4.2 Current Generation

A Chroma 61605 is computer controlled in frequency and amplitude via a DA converter, e.g. NI USB 6216, which current is feeding a Nokia step-up transformer. The computer interface can either lock-in to the local power frequency or be run at 50 or 60 Hz with a general mixture of harmonics up to 2 kHz synchronized or free-running via an Agilent 33500B.

One generator is injecting the fundamental 50 Hz combined with an odd harmonic, e.g. 150 Hz, 250 Hz, ... using the Chroma 61605. This at the same time combined with supraharmonic frequencies is generated with the Clarke-Hess 8200 close to 2 kHz, 5 kHz, 10 kHz and 20 kHz up to 100 A, and 50 kHz, 100 kHz and 150 kHz up to 20 A, while avoiding multiples of the fundamental frequency. The limiting factor for the currents above 20 kHz was the compliance voltage from the inductance in the loop where the Clarke-Hess 8200 can drive up to 7 V.

4.4.3 Measurement System

A HITEC Zero-Flux core is used for measurement of the signals from the line frequency and harmonics thereof. The signal is sampled by one of the PXIe-6396 channels measuring the line frequency and harmonics current.

Figure 10. Schematic of the RISE set-up.

The supraharmonics are generated from a computer-controlled Keysight 33500B driving a modified Clarke-Hess 8200 amplifier. In this manner a line frequency/phase and frequency independent current with single frequency or spectrum of supraharmonics is generated from 2 to 150 kHz. From a 100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D (RISE model) the voltage is sampled by one of the PXIe-6396 channels measuring the supraharmonic current. The computer program gives the fundamental and/or one or several harmonics feeding the Chroma 61605 generator and a mixture of supraharmonics to the Clarke Hess. The fundamental can be synchronized with the grid line frequency. The set-up is shown in Figure 10.

The components in Figure 10 and their functions are the following:

- Core controller - LabVIEW program "Follower": This program generates signals for the testing and slowly ramps up and down the currents to avoid overvoltage from inductances or transients. The program also collects the signals from the three CTs via a PXIe-6396 digitizer.
- Digitizer PXIe-6396: The signals from the reference CTs, i.e. a HITEC 500/2000 or 6000A (peak current) measuring the line frequency and harmonics and a current shunt RISE CS2D measures the supraharmonics up to 100 A, are sampled by this digitizer. The digitizer has 8 channels simultaneously sampled, 18 bits resolution and a sampling rate up to 15 MS/s. Supraharmonics are sampled at least with a sampling rate = 2^n , larger than $5 \cdot 150$ kS/s (7 periods), which is $2^{20} = 1.05$ MS/s. This choice is for adaptation to the FFT analysis to avoid spectral leakage. The sampling length is dictated by the line frequency, i.e. a duration of at least 7 periods of 50Hz = 140 ms, rounded to 200 ms, about 200 kS.

- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (Agilent 33500B): Samples the power line frequency for generation of true voltage and harmonics via a computer controller (LabVIEW “follower”). The 33500B generates the waveshapes for suprahharmonics and controls the output of the generator Clarke-Hess 8200.
- Arbitrary Waveform Generator (NI-USB 6216): Provides a wave shape output with programmable amplitude and frequency (50 Hz to 1 kHz). This signal can be synchronized to the line frequency and can contain harmonics with amplitude and relative phase.
- A Chroma type 61605 4 kVA generator is used to generate currents controlled by the NI-USB 6216 arbitrary wave form generator via an external input from 15 – 1000 Hz with 32A/20A (150V/300V) ranges. Using a step-up transformer 100:1 the maximum current is 3.2 kA.
- A modified transconductance amplifier Clarke-Hess 8200 is used for generation of suprahharmonics up to 150 kHz. The amplifier can generate 100 A up to 20 kHz and 20 A up to 150 kHz, limited by the compliance voltage of 7V. The waveshape of the amplifier is controlled by the computer program via an Agilent 33500B.

4.4.4 Results

The Current sensor Pearson 301X was used to test the system. This sensor can measure up to 400 A and is designed for impulse current measurements. A mixed signal of 50 and 150 Hz, with amplitudes up to 365 A @ 50 Hz and 35 A @ 150 Hz was generated with the Chroma 61605 + transformer and several suprahharmonic signals around 20 A from 2 to 150 kHz were injected with the Clarke-Hess 8200. In Figure 11 the ratio error and phase error are plotted. The Pearson 301X is apparently not very good at lower frequencies which was expected from the impulse design. For the suprahharmonics it behaves well and is within 0.08% for the ratio and within 3% phase error. calibrations

Figure 11. Results for a Pearson 301X impulse current sensor.

A Rogowski coil PEM CWT15 was selected for use in substation monitoring. Preliminary results are 0.03% ratio error and 22 mrad phase displacement at 50 Hz. The frequency dependence is to be characterized.

4.4.5 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

Traceability of the measurement systems of RISE is ensured by the calibration of a HITEC Zero-Flux 2000 A up to 1 kA and 1 kHz, or a HITEC Zero-Flux 6000 A up to 2 kA and 1 kHz, using a step-up procedure referenced to the primary 100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D. From the HITEC Zero-Flux the traceability for the DUT of the line frequency and harmonics up to 1 kHz is realised. Traceability for the suprahharmonics 9 – 150 kHz is realised by the 100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D itself.

The 8 ch simultaneous sampling digitizer PXIe 6396 is traceable up to 150 kHz from Fluke calibrator 5700A. The time lag between the channels is mapped for contribution to phase uncertainties from the current sensors. The expanded measurement uncertainty from PXIe-6396 is better than 180, 330, 800 and 1500 $\mu\text{V/V}$ for 1, 2, 5 and 10 V range. Using a For HITEC 2000 an expanded measurement uncertainty of 1500 $\mu\text{V/V}$ with max 1.4 kA fundamental freq. Instead, using a HITEC Zero-flux 6000A core, 2 kA rms can be sampled with the 5V

range and hence 800 $\mu\text{V/V}$, which is the selection for the system. The phase uncertainty for the 6000A core is 1.0 mrad

The chosen DUT, the PEM CWT15 has a sensitivity 2 mV/A. for suprahomonics typical voltage levels observed are 40 A at 45 kHz, which translates to 80 mV output and the 1V range of the PXIe-6396 with an exp unc. of 180 $\mu\text{V/V}$. The noise level of the PEM is 7 mV max pk-pk, which gives an uncertainty contribution of 3%. Using the designed bandpass amplifier with 10x amplification the output increase to 800 mV. For this the 2V range is used with 0.033 % uncertainty and a 0.3% noise contribution. Increasing the amplification to 50x the output is 4 V with an uncertainty of 0.08 % and noise contribution of 0.06%. The conclusion is that for matching of noise from the PEM with the digitizer uncertainty the amplification in the bandpass filter will be optimal for 50x. Since we are analysing the signals using FFT the noise is suppressed by 20 dB or more, thus reducing the amplification to 10x the noise is reduced to contribute 0.03% or less, which would be an optimal trade-off.

100A DSWM current shunt type CS2D the expanded measurement unc. at 150 kHz is 0.0150% for the ratio and 2.5 mrad for the phase angle.

The combined expanded uncertainty for the calibration of ratio at 150 kHz is $< \pm 0.16\%$ and phase displacement is 2.5 mrad. The combined expanded uncertainty for the calibration of ratio < 1 kHz is $< \pm 0.02\%$ and phase displacement is 1 mrad.

4.5 VTT, Finland

4.5.1 Low-current multitone harmonics system

VTT system for generation and measurement of 50 Hz fundamental and harmonics is show in Figure 12. A signal with up to 10 frequency components is created, and it is uploaded to the two-channel arbitrary waveform generator (AWG, Keysight 33500B). One channel of the AWG feeds the transconductance amplifier (Guildline 7620), and the other channel provides a synchronized trigger signal to the two-channel digitizer (Applicos WFD20). A wideband shunt is used as the reference for calibration of current sensors or shunts. The system is controlled by a PC.

As the sampling is coherent with the multitone reference signal, no windowing is needed, and each generated harmonic will fall in one FTT bin without spectral leakage.

Figure 13 shows an example of a recorded frequency response of a wideband current sensor (Pearson 110A) between 50 Hz and 150 Hz.

Figure 12. VTT multitone generation and measurement setup.

Figure 13. An example of a measured multitone waveform. Even though the signal level is low, the signal-to-noise ratio is c. 75 dB.

4.5.2 High-current low frequency system

This multitone current generation system can be used together with VTT high-current system for power frequency calibration. The high-current generator has a bandwidth up to 1 kHz, and it can generate up to 8 kA at 50 Hz. This system can be used together with the multitone system for calibration of supraharmonics of window type measurement systems. One source generates 50 Hz or 60 Hz up to 8 kA and the other source generates supraharmonics from DC to 100 kHz up to 20 A and 2 A for frequencies up to 1 MHz. The device under test (DUT) is then connected to both sources.

4.5.3 Traceability and Typical Uncertainties

The metrological traceability of the system is ensured through the set of wideband reference shunts. The shunts are calibrated from 50 Hz to 100 kHz and their AC/DC ratio is characterized to be in the ppm range through all frequencies.

The combined uncertainty for the ratio is less than 0.1% up to 150 kHz. The combined uncertainty for the overall phase displacement of the calibration set up is less than 2 crad in the same frequency range.

5 Traceability and Measurement Uncertainty

5.1 General Traceability Concepts

The reference current measurement systems described in Section 4 have been developed to provide traceable characterisation of current transformers over an extended range of current and frequency up to 150 kHz. Although the technical implementations differ between the participating laboratories, the traceability follows a common metrological approach. In all cases, the measurement result is linked to the SI through calibrated electrical quantities such as resistance, voltage, current, and time or frequency, combined with frequency-dependent characterisation of the reference sensors and acquisition channels.

At VSL, for example, traceability is realised either by direct comparison of a 100:1 reference CT with calibrated 1 A and 5 A broadband shunts, or by direct primary–secondary measurement using a calibrated wideband power analyser. At METAS, traceability is established through calibrated current shunts and calibrated voltage channels of the analyser. At FFII, the wideband clamp used as reference is calibrated against a coaxial AC/DC shunt. At RISE, the traceability chain combines zero-flux current transformers, a broadband current shunt, and a calibrated digitiser. At VTT, traceability is based on a set of wideband reference shunts whose AC/DC ratio has been characterised over the relevant frequency range.

5.2 Reference Sensors

A key outcome of Task 3.2 is the identification, development, and use of suitable reference current sensors for wideband traceable measurements. The implemented systems use several classes of reference elements, each with its own advantages and limitations. These include electronically compensated reference CTs, zero-flux current transformers, broadband current shunts, Hall-effect current transducers, wideband current clamps, and Rogowski-type current sensors. The choice of reference element depends on the current range, required bandwidth, target uncertainty, and practical complexity of the measurement chain.

For the highest current levels, reference CTs remain attractive because they allow scaling of kiloampere primary currents to manageable secondary currents without dissipating large amounts of power in shunts. This principle is used, for example, in the VSL system, where the DUT is compared against an NRC electronically compensated reference CT, and in the RISE setup, where HITEC zero-flux current transformers are used for the fundamental and lower harmonics. These reference transformers provide very low errors at low frequency, but their high-frequency behaviour depends on the bandwidth of internal feedback and compensation electronics. The report therefore makes clear that their use above a few kilohertz requires dedicated characterisation and careful uncertainty assignment.

Broadband current shunts are used either as the primary reference element or as a calibration artefact within the traceability chain. Their main advantage is a well-defined current-to-voltage transfer with comparatively simple modelling of frequency dependence. This is the basis of the METAS and VTT systems and also forms part of the VSL and RISE traceability routes. Wideband shunts are particularly suitable for frequencies above several kilohertz, but at very high current levels they are less practical because of dissipation and construction constraints.

5.3 Comparator Systems

The required comparator functionality is realised in different ways. VSL, METAS, and FFII use a Yokogawa WT5000 wideband power analyser as a synchronous sampling comparator, measuring either two secondary currents directly or current-related voltages derived from shunts. RISE uses a multi-channel PXIe-6396 digitiser with simultaneous sampling, allowing coherent analysis of multiple channels over a broad frequency range. VTT uses an Applicos WFD20 digitiser in combination with coherent multitone generation. In all cases, one essential development has been the extension of the comparator functionality beyond the classical 50/60 Hz range toward at least 150 kHz, including attention to channel gain, inter-channel phase deviation, synchronisation, and spectral processing.

The upgrades reported in this deliverable are therefore not limited to a single comparator hardware design. Rather, they comprise the development of complete wideband comparator systems, including calibrated input channels, synchronised acquisition, suitable signal ranges, and processing methods capable of determining ratio and phase over the full frequency range of interest. This is one of the key technical results of the work described in Section 4.

5.4 Frequency Dependent Effects

At frequencies up to 150 kHz, the uncertainty is influenced not only by the calibration of the reference sensor itself, but also by the combined effect of cables, grounding arrangements, parasitic inductances and capacitances, burden conditions, and the bandwidth of the acquisition channels. In several of the reported systems, these effects become the dominant contributors to the uncertainty above approximately 10 kHz.

For this reason, all participating laboratories explicitly characterise frequency-dependent effects in their traceability chains. Examples include calibration of shunts over frequency, calibration of analyser voltage or current channels using reference calibrators, mapping of inter-channel time delay in digitiser systems, and evaluation of the influence of cable routing, connector choice, and grounding. In the VSL wideband CT system, practical setup choices such as range selection, cabling, and grounding were found to have a measurable impact on the final uncertainty. At METAS, corrections are applied to account for gain and phase errors in the measurement channels. At RISE, the digitiser timing and the channel-to-channel phase behaviour are explicitly included.

5.5 Uncertainty Evaluation Methodology

The uncertainty evaluations associated with the reference current measurement systems follow the general principles of the Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM), in which all relevant input quantities are identified, quantified, and propagated to the measurand. Depending on the system, the measurand is either the complex ratio error of the DUT relative to a reference current sensor or the ratio and phase relationship between the primary and secondary quantities of the DUT. In both cases, the uncertainty associated with the result is frequency dependent and, in some cases, also current dependent.

The dominant uncertainty contributions reported in Section 4 may be grouped into several categories:

- Reference sensor uncertainty, including amplitude and phase uncertainty of the reference CT, current shunt, current clamp, or other reference device.
- Acquisition system uncertainty, including gain error, linearity, inter-channel phase deviation, timing error, and range-selection effects of the power analyser or digitiser.
- Frequency-dependent setup effects, such as cable impedance, connector repeatability, parasitic inductive or capacitive coupling, grounding arrangements, and burden effects.
- Signal-related effects, including signal-to-noise ratio, repeatability, residual drift, waveform stability, and spectral leakage or fitting residuals in the signal-processing stage.
- Scaling and auxiliary elements, such as multi-turn arrangements, current buffers, compensation electronics, and any auxiliary ratio stages required to bring the signals into a suitable range.

In the lower-frequency range, uncertainty is often dominated by the calibration of the reference sensor and by the gain and phase accuracy of the instrument channels. At higher frequencies, setup-dependent phase effects, bandwidth limitations, and parasitic couplings become increasingly important. This trend is visible throughout the systems described in Section 4: VSL reports uncertainties of the order of parts in 10^{-4} for the shunt-supported high-accuracy route at 150 kHz, while simplified direct measurement routes are closer to parts in 10^{-3} . METAS reports amplitude uncertainties of a few hundred parts in 10^{-6} and phase uncertainties of a few tenths of a milliradian. RISE reports combined expanded uncertainties below 0.16 % and 2.5 mrad at 150 kHz, and VTT reports ratio uncertainties below 0.1 % up to 150 kHz. FFII reports higher uncertainties, reaching the percent level at the top of the frequency range, consistent with the chosen reference transducer and measurement chain.

A complete uncertainty budget should therefore always be provided together with the specific measurement configuration to which it applies. In practice, multiple budgets may be needed for a single system, for example

as a function of frequency band, current range, or chosen traceability route. This is especially relevant when a system offers both a high-accuracy reference mode and a simplified routine-measurement mode.

5.6 Example Uncertainty Budget

The uncertainty budgets described by the partners are not fully uniform in structure, because the systems differ in architecture and intended use. The following tables provide illustrative examples of uncertainty budgets for magnitude (ratio) and phase displacement at a frequency of 150 kHz. The values are indicative and are intended to demonstrate a suitable structure for reporting and interpreting uncertainty contributions in wideband current measurements.

Source of uncertainty (magnitude)	Evaluation method	Standard uncertainty
Reference sensor calibration	Type B	50 ppm
Acquisition channel gain ratio	Type B	80 ppm
Cable and connector effects	Type B	100 ppm
Grounding / parasitic coupling	Type B	80 ppm
Signal processing / fitting residuals	Type B	40 ppm
Repeatability	Type A	30 ppm

Source of uncertainty (phase)	Evaluation method	Standard uncertainty
Reference sensor calibration	Type B	0.10 mrad
Inter-channel phase deviation	Type B	0.15 mrad
Cable and connector phase effects	Type B	0.10 mrad
Grounding / parasitic coupling	Type B	0.10 mrad
Signal processing / fitting residuals	Type B	0.05 mrad
Repeatability	Type A	0.05 mrad

For this example, the combined standard uncertainty in amplitude is of the order of 150–200 ppm, and the combined standard uncertainty in phase is of the order of 0.2–0.3 mrad. Using a coverage factor $k = 2$, the resulting expanded uncertainty would be of the order of 300–400 ppm in amplitude and 0.4–0.6 mrad in phase. These values are representative of a well-characterised high-accuracy wideband ratio system and are broadly consistent with the best performance levels reported in Section 4. By contrast, simplified systems or systems employing reference sensors with stronger frequency dependence may yield substantially larger uncertainties, especially near the upper end of the investigated frequency range.

6 Discussion and Conclusion

The reference current measurement systems developed within Task 3.2 enable traceable characterisation of current transformers up to 2 kA and frequencies up to 150 kHz. The presented approaches demonstrate that both high-accuracy comparator-based systems and simplified sampling-based methods can be extended into

the supraharmonic frequency range, provided that frequency-dependent effects are properly characterised and accounted for.

The achieved uncertainties, ranging from parts in 10^{-4} for high-accuracy reference systems to parts in 10^{-3} for simplified methods, are suitable for the intended applications and provide a solid metrological basis for further development of calibration services.

The results establish a sound foundation for future work on wideband instrument transformer calibration and contribute to ongoing standardisation efforts in this field.

7 References

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